

The role of emotional intelligence and gender in the association between maternal attachment and anxiety in youth: A moderated mediation model

Yimin Zhong, Zhuofeng Li, & Dennis Relajo-Howell
University of Edinburgh (United Kingdom)

lipiandex@gmail.com

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Anxiety is associated with negative outcomes such as behaviour disorder and suicide. Previous literature has established the association between maternal attachment and anxiety. However, the effects of emotional intelligence and gender on the pathway are understudied among older adolescents and young adults. The study aims to investigate the potential mediating effect of emotional intelligence in the association between maternal attachment and anxiety in youth, with a consideration of gender as a moderator that may influence the strength of the indirect effect. Adolescents and young adults ($N = 239$) completed a set of scales measuring their maternal attachment, trait emotional intelligence and anxiety level. Analysis was based on the existing dataset and obtained ethical approval. A PROCESS macro was employed for mediation and moderation analysis. The results indicated that emotional intelligence mediated the association between maternal attachment and anxiety. Furthermore, moderated mediation analysis showed a significant indirect effect from maternal attachment to anxiety through emotional intelligence in females but not in males, with gender moderated the pathway from emotional intelligence to anxiety. The results highlight the importance of trait emotional intelligence and gender pathways in the development of anxiety. Emotional intelligence only mediates the relationship between maternal attachment and anxiety in female adolescents and young adults. However, the moderating effect of gender should be carefully generalised due to potential problems.

Keywords: anxiety; emotional intelligence; gender; maternal attachment; moderated mediation

Anxiety has been robustly associated with mother-adolescent attachment (Colonnaesi et al., 2011; Nielsen et al., 2017b; van Eijck et al., 2012). It is crucial to reduce anxiety in adolescence and young adulthood since anxiety is linked to severe psychopathology in adulthood (Mohammadi et al., 2020; Woodward & Fergusson, 2001). Emotional intelligence has been considered as a crucial factor in the development of anxiety, and gender may impact how emotional intelligence contributes to anxiety among adolescents and young people (Karakuş, 2013; Salguero & Extremera et al., 2012).

However, the mechanism contributing to anxiety is understudied. The purpose of the current study is to investigate whether emotional intelligence mediates the relationship between maternal attachment and anxiety and whether the effect of emotional intelligence on anxiety is contingent upon gender. The identification of mechanisms contributing to anxiety will deepen the understanding of anxiety and help to provide more constructive suggestions for anxiety intervention.

Attachment and anxiety

Anxiety has been increasingly popular among adolescents and young adults. The lifetime prevalence rate of anxiety-related disorders (ADs) was 4.11% in mainland China from 2000 to 2015, with a dramatic increase from 2011 onwards (Guo et al., 2016). During the COVID-19 pandemic, a study including students aged 12-18 years old assessed anxiety and depression symptoms using the Generalized Anxiety Disorder (GAD-7) questionnaire. It was found that the prevalence rate of anxiety was 37.4%. Such findings were consistent with the meta-analysis conducted by Ghandour et al. (2025), in which 13 studies on anxiety during the COVID-19 pandemic were examined, showing a 26% prevalence rate of anxiety among children and adolescents. Anxiety was associated with negative mental health conditions, including behavioural disorders (Mohammadi et al., 2020), emotion dysregulation (Bender et al., 2012). It also acted as a risk factor for major depression, drug abuse and suicidal behaviour (Woodward & Fergusson, 2001). Therefore, it was important to relieve and mitigate anxiety.

It was crucial to explore relevant risk and protective factors giving rise to the aetiology and maintenance of anxiety symptoms. Attachment was a significant factor influencing the development of anxiety. According to Bowlby (1982), secure attachment was gradually formed through the consistent and predictable interactions with the caregiver in times of infant distress. Securely attached individuals were inclined to using their caregiver as a “secure base”, in which soothing, comfort and sensitive responses would be provided timely to relieve fear and distress they experienced in the exploration of the environment. However, insecurely attached individuals might have an inconsistent caregiver, which meant that the availability and the sensitivity from the caregiver were changeable and unpredictable. Thus, they were uncertain and concerned about the availability of attachment figures (Bowlby, 1982). The sense of uncertainty might be internalised in the internal working model (IWM) and be generalised to broader social contexts during adolescence. Therefore, insecure attachment could be theoretically linked to adolescent anxiety due to a sense of uncertainty towards other people and the environment, which was originally derived from inconsistent responses from the caregiver.

Consistent with this idea, many studies found that early parental attachment is consistently associated with anxiety symptoms among children and adolescents (Bender et al., 2012; Colonnaesi et al., 2011; Warren et al., 1997). Specifically, the quality of parental attachment predicted anxiety among delinquent adolescents (Bonab & Koohsar, 2011), and mother-child attachment was negatively related to social anxiety symptoms (Brumariu & Kerns, 2008). Besides, a meta-analysis of 46 studies was conducted and it showed an effect size of $r = 0.30$, indicating that attachment

insecurity was moderately related to anxiety in children and adolescents (Colonnesi et al., 2011). However, the strength of effect size was dependent on age. Specifically, such an association was significantly stronger during adolescence compared to childhood. It could be inferred that adolescence was more sensitive to anxiety than childhood. Moreover, there was no difference found between the relationships of anxiety disorders with attachment and anxiety symptoms with attachment. This indicated that the effect size of attachment insecurity on anxiety-related disorders was not significantly different from that on anxiety symptoms, suggesting a stable correlation. Thus, it could be revealed that attachment insecurity was constantly associated with anxiety. Given that most studies found that early attachment could predict anxiety in children and adolescents (Bender et al., 2012; Colonnesi et al., 2011; Goodwin & Styron, 2012), we suggested that insecure attachment was a potential high-risk factor for adolescent anxiety. In addition, it was suggested that the developmental stage might play a crucial role in the development of anxiety. Many studies focused on children and young adolescents under 16 years old, but only limited research focused on the development of anxiety in those aged 16-25 years old (Bonab & Koohsar, 2011; Colonnesi et al., 2011). Since adolescence and early adulthood was a sensitive period for developing psychosocial vulnerability (Collins et al., 2002), this study would select elderly adolescents and young adults aged 16–25 years old to examine the impact of maternal attachment on anxiety during late adolescence and early adulthood.

Attachment and emotional intelligence

Despite that there was strong evidence supporting the link between parent-adolescent attachment and anxiety, the specific mechanism was understudied. It was proposed that insecure attachment was a nonspecific risk factor for psychopathology (Mikulincer et al., 2003). Thus, the mediating factors and the mechanisms needed to be explored, among which emotional intelligence was a crucial one since it can be manipulated and trained so as to regulate emotions (Li et al., 2009; Nielsen et al., 2017a; Unni, 2015). Emotional intelligence (EI) referred to a set of capabilities of perceiving, understanding, and managing emotions (García-Sancho et al., 2014). The ability model defined EI as capabilities concerning emotional information processing (Lopes et al., 2003). By contrast, the trait model considered EI as a personality constructs (Petrides & Mavroveli, 2018). Since ability EI might not be precisely measured by questionnaires, this study would focus on self-report trait EI, which was a multifaceted construct consisting of several sub-dimensions. Trait EI was classified into emotional appraisal and expression, emotional regulation and emotional utilisation (Schutte et al., 1998). Moreover, Ciarrochi et al. (2001) proposed four dimensions of EI, including emotional perception, self-emotion management, managing others' emotions and emotional utilisation. In general, it has been revealed that emotional intelligence incorporates the ability of emotion regulation.

Secure attachment may contribute to the development of emotional intelligence, as reflected in one's ability to manage emotions. Research has shown that secure attachment is positively associated with emotional understanding and regulation (Kafetsios, 2004). Children and young people with a high quality of secure attachment are more capable of regulating fear and anxiety (Dykas & Cassidy, 2011). Moreover, they demonstrate greater emotional regulatory self-efficacy (Pan et al., 2016), as they tend to hold more positive beliefs about their ability to manage emotions compared to those with insecure attachment styles (Mikulincer et al., 2003). In line with previous findings, Unni (2015) reported that individuals with stronger parent–adolescent attachment scored higher on emotional intelligence, further suggesting a positive association between attachment and emotional intelligence. Other studies have similarly identified a positive relationship between attachment security and emotional intelligence (Li et al., 2009; Nielsen et al., 2017a). Based on these findings, it can be inferred that securely attached individuals are more likely to develop adaptive emotion regulation strategies than those with insecure attachment.

In contrast, insecure attachment might decrease the level of emotional intelligence and led to adolescent anxiety. Despite that insecure attachment was not a casual factor of anxiety-related psychopathology, but the chronic use of hyperactivating or deactivating strategies was found to put children and adolescents at a higher risk of developing mental health issues (Lee et al., 2022). Insecurely attached individuals were prone to employing maladaptive emotional strategies, namely deactivating and hyperactivating strategies (Mikulincer et al., 2003). Deactivation of the attachment system was generally adopted by those with insecure-avoidant attachment. As a consequence of having an unavailable and rejecting caregiver, they tended to suppress negative emotions as a deactivating strategy since suppression could act as a defence mechanism to prevent interpersonal threats (Bourne et al., 2022) and to detach themselves from processing distressing social information (Mazzone et al., 2021). Although deactivation strategy might help to regulate emotions in the short term, it might reduce the ability to understand and utilise emotions encompassed in one's emotional intelligence capability and thus result in internalising problems such as anxiety (Pace et al., 2016). In contrast, hyperactivating strategies were commonly employed among individuals with insecure anxious attachment. They were likely to exhibit exaggerated behaviours such as losing their temper and acting out to seek attention and obtain expected responses from the attachment figure.

Hyperactivation strategy acted as a compensation strategy to seek care and love from the caregiver and meet relevant needs by escalating negative emotions and poor behaviour. The strategy of hyperactivation might also deteriorate emotional intelligence since it does not contribute to emotional management. Both hyperactivating and deactivating strategies were maladaptive emotional regulation strategies, followed by the failure of distress-soothing responses (Navas-Casado et al., 2023). The development of emotional intelligence was likely to be affected by maladaptive emotion regulation strategies deriving from insecure attachment patterns. As for the relationship between insecure attachment and emotional intelligence, a recent meta-analysis including 26 studies examined the association between attachment and emotional intelligence in the non-clinical adult sample (Walker et al., 2022). They found that trait emotional intelligence was negatively linked to both anxious attachment ($r = -0.25$) and avoidant attachment ($r = -0.36$), suggesting a small to moderate negative correlation. This was to say that higher attachment insecurity was linked to lower trait emotional intelligence. This idea was consistently supported by many cross-sectional studies demonstrating that attachment insecurity could negatively predict emotional intelligence (Brumariu et al., 2012; Lanciano et al., 2012; Marks et al., 2016; Scarlat, 2021) among children, adolescents and young adults while limited studies found a reversed correlation. Given relevant theories and empirical evidence, therefore, we posited that emotional intelligence (EI) could be predicted from maternal attachment security.

Anxiety and emotional intelligence

Theories of emotional intelligence (EI) proposed that the extent to which adolescents perceived and regulated emotions was associated with a lower possibility of emotion-related psychopathologies such as anxiety (Lopes et al., 2004). Emotion regulation ability encompassed in emotional intelligence might partially explain the development of anxiety. Those with a lower ability to regulate emotions might fail to suppress negative emotions and thus develop more anxious and depressive emotions. Plus, emotional clarity, which referred to the ability to understand emotions, may help individuals adjust their behaviours to the demands of social situations accordingly (Cejudo et al., 2018). Without emotional clarity, individuals were confused about the emotions of the self and others and had no idea how to behave appropriately. The inability to understand emotions might increase the uncertainty of interacting with others during adolescence and thus lead to anxiety. A meta-analysis found that trait EI was found to have a more significant predicting effect on mental health than ability EI (Martins et al., 2010). We suggested that trait emotional intelligence as

a personality construct is likely to influence the development of anxiety during adolescence and young adulthood.

Research has stressed the importance of emotional regulation in the development of anxiety. It was found that adolescents with higher EI showed a lower level of anxiety (Resurrección et al., 2014). Moreover, the anxiety level was found to be negatively associated with emotional intelligence, and anxiety could be predicted from emotional intelligence (Hassan & Achugbu, 2010; Mashhadi, 2010; Morón & Biolik-Morón, 2021; Resurrección et al., 2014). Specifically, both emotional clarity and emotional repair were negatively linked to anxiety and emotional repair capacity was a significant predictor for anxiety symptoms (García-Sancho et al., 2014). Consistent with previous findings, Mashhadi (2010) found that both emotional repair and clarity could predict general anxiety symptoms. Therefore, it was proposed that anxiety is the result of emotional dysregulation (Wołyńczyk-Gmaj et al., 2022). However, the causal direction between anxiety and emotional intelligence was unclear. In a longitudinal study, the authors measured self-report emotional intelligence consisting of attention to feelings, emotional clarity, and emotional repair by using TMMS (Trait Meta-Mood Scale). They found that a higher level of emotional repair was associated with a low level of anxiety ($r = -0.12$), though the effect was small. Besides, both emotional clarity and repair could negatively predict anxiety at Time 1, but anxiety at Time 2 could not be predicted from emotional clarity and emotional repair at Time 1 (Salguero & Palomera et al., 2012). It is suggested that emotional intelligence may not be a casual contributor to anxiety, and they may contribute to one another in a dynamic interplay.

Hofmann and colleague (209) highlighted the central role of emotion regulation in the aetiology and maintenance of anxiety. Many studies found that emotion regulation played a mediating role in the relationship between attachment and anxiety among adolescents and adults (Bender et al., 2012; Nielsen et al., 2017b; Read et al., 2018). However, few studies have examined the mediating effect of emotional intelligence in the association between attachment and anxiety (e.g., Acharya & Rejojo, 2017; Borawski et al., 2022; Pilao et al., 2016). Given that emotional intelligence was a multifaceted construct including emotional understanding, expression and regulation, we proposed that emotional intelligence might influence the link between attachment and anxiety. By now, we have synthesised the evidence between these three variables (a) attachment and anxiety (e.g., Colonnese et al., 2011; Nielsen et al., 2017b; van Eijck et al., 2012), (b) attachment and emotion intelligence (e.g., Kafetsios, 2004; Lanciano et al., 2012; Scarlat, 2021; Walker et al., 2022), and (c) emotion intelligence and anxiety (e.g., Hassan & Achugbu, 2010; Mashhadi, 2010; Resurrección et al., 2014). Therefore, it is posited that emotional intelligence will mediate the association between attachment and anxiety.

Gender as a moderator

Females may be at a higher risk of developing anxiety than males. A socio-demographic study indicated that the female gender was a higher risk factor for anxiety symptoms (Zhou et al., 2020). Chang (2018) found that gender differences could significantly predict anxious symptoms. It was suggested that females were more vulnerable to anxiety than males (Silberg et al., 2001), which was supported previous findings demonstrating a higher level of anxiety in females than in males (Collins et al., 2002; Fernández-Merino, 2020; Karakuş, 2013). Therefore, we proposed that females would have higher levels of anxiety than males in the present study.

Growing evidence has revealed gender differences in the level of emotional intelligence. It was found that the ability emotional intelligence was higher among adolescent females than males (Salguero & Palomera et al., 2012). Other studies also found such a pattern in terms of the trait emotional intelligence (Ciarrochi et al., 2001; Śmieja et al., 2014; Wojciechowski et al., 2014).

However, there were contradictory findings suggesting that females had lower emotional intelligence than males (Karakuş, 2013). Consistent with this study, (Gomez-Baya et al., 2017) conducted a longitudinal study for two years and found a consistent gender difference that females had low levels of emotional intelligence than males throughout the period of mid-adolescence. As a consequence, females developed more anxiety symptoms than males during mid-adolescence. Given the inconsistent findings of gender differences in emotional intelligence, this study would examine the gender differences in the level of anxiety and emotional intelligence. Further, many studies found that ability emotional intelligence significantly predicted depression, deviant behaviour, poorer peer relationship only in males but not in females (Karakuş, 2013; Lopes et al., 2004; Salguero & Extremera et al., 2012), suggesting that gender might act as a moderator in the association between emotional intelligence and mental health outcomes. To the author's knowledge, there was no study examining whether the effect of trait emotional intelligence on anxiety was contingent upon gender. Only some studies found a moderating effect of gender in the association between emotional intelligence and depression (Karakuş, 2013; Salguero & Extremera et al., 2012). Therefore, it was necessary to take gender into consideration in exploring the effect of emotional intelligence on anxiety. This study aims to explore the moderating effect of gender in the indirect effect of maternal attachment on anxiety through emotional intelligence. Specifically, we presume that gender can moderate the strength of relationships between emotional intelligence and anxiety. Figure 1 shows the conceptual model of hypothesised moderated mediation. And a series of hypotheses are listed below, as previously discussed.

Figure 1
The conceptual model of hypothesised moderated mediation

- H1: Maternal attachment will have a negative effect on anxiety in adolescents and young people.
- H2: Maternal attachment will positively predict emotional intelligence.
- H3: Emotional intelligence will mediate the relationship between maternal attachment and anxiety.
- H4: Gender will moderate the relationship between emotional intelligence and anxiety.

METHODOLOGY

Participants

We collected 283 valid questionnaires. Although only maternal attachment would be included as the independent variable, only those who completed both maternal and paternal attachment scales were included in analyses to ensure that participants were from a two-parent family. Forty-two

participants who did not complete both maternal and paternal attachment was excluded from the original sample since it was unknown whether those who completed either maternal or paternal attachment were not conscientious, or they were from a single-parent family. To complete the survey, participants must have used English as the primary language of communication for at least two years in the experiences. Otherwise, they were not allowed to participate in the survey. Given that gender would be incorporated as a moderator, two participants who did not report their gender was excluded. After data exclusion, participants included in the study were 239 adolescents and young adults aged 16–25 years old ($M = 21.31$, $SD = 2.91$), with 18% men ($N = 43$) and 82% women ($N = 196$). Out of the 239 participants, 193 resided in the UK (80.75%) and 22 participants lived in the rest of Europe (9.21%), which consisted of a majority of this sample (90.00%). The rest participants were from Asia, Australia, North America and South America, with the proportion of 6.69%, 1.26%, 1.26% and 0.84%.

With G* power software, the power analysis was performed to detect the required sample size for moderated mediation analysis (Faul et al., 2007). The power was set to 0.80 and the significance level was set to 0.05. The number of predictors was set to four since there would be an independent variable, a moderator, a mediator and an interaction term predicting the dependent variable in the moderated mediation model. The estimated sample size to identify a significant moderate effect was 85. Thus, the sample size in the present study ($N = 239$) was considered powerful enough to detect a medium effect size.

Measures

Generalized Anxiety Disorder questionnaire (GAD-7)

GAD-7 consists of 7 items measuring the most salient diagnostic symptoms of generalised anxiety disorder. A 4-point Likert scale was employed in the scale from 0 = not at all to 3 = nearly every day. Higher overall scores indicate more severe anxiety symptoms. Specifically, overall scores falling within 5–9 was considered as mild and overall scores falling within 10–14 was considered as moderate anxiety, and an overall score ranging from 15 to 21 represented severe anxiety symptoms (Spitzer et al., 2006). Previous findings suggested that it had good internal reliability, with Cronbach's alpha between 0.85 and 0.92 (He et al., 2010; Rutter & Brown, 2017; Spitzer et al., 2006). The Cronbach's alpha of GAD-7 is 0.91 in the present study.

Inventory of Parental and Peer Attachment (IPPA)

The quality of maternal attachment was measured by the subscale of Inventory of Parent and Peer Attachment (Armsden & Greenberg, 1987). The IPPA was originally developed to measure adolescents' perceived attachment quality with parents and peers for those aged 16–20 (Armsden & Greenberg, 1987). The mother, father and peer version of IPPA was employed. It consists of 25 items for each section and three sub-dimensions are assessed, including trust, communication and alienation. The communication sub-scale measured the quality of communication between adolescents and parents. The trust sub-scale assessed the degree to which adolescents trusted parents to respect and accept their feelings. The alienation sub-scale evaluated the extent of negative feelings towards parents. Items were rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1=Almost Never or Never True to 5 = Almost Always or Always True), with higher overall scores indicating a higher quality of attachment relationships. Moreover, items 3, 6, 9, 14 in the maternal attachment scale were reverse scored. The IPPA was proven to have good reliability with 0.87 for maternal attachment and 0.89 for paternal attachment, respectively (Lim et al., 2015). Thus, it has been revealed that IPPA is a reliable measurement. Since our hypotheses are not relevant to peer

attachment, it will not be incorporated into the analysis. The Cronbach's alpha of maternal attachment is 0.96 in the current study.

Schutte Self-Report Emotional Intelligence scale (SSREI)

To measure emotional intelligence (EI), we employed a 33-items questionnaire developed by Schutte et al. (1998) based on the theoretical model of EI from Salovey and Mayer (1990). Although the developer did not clarify the corresponding items for each sub-dimension of the SSREI scale in the original study of Schutte et al. (1998), recent studies employing confirmatory factor analysis showed that there were four sub-dimensions in SSREI scale, including emotional perception, managing others' emotions, self-emotion management and emotional utilisation (Ciarrochi et al., 2001). Emotional perception referred to the capability of understanding and discerning one's own and others' emotion. Managing others emotions referred to the extent to which adolescents expressed emotions and behaved appropriately to take care of the others' emotions such as making others feel better when they were down. In other words, this sub-dimension was about caring for others' emotions and adjusting their own behaviours. Self-emotion management was defined as the ability to adaptively cope with negative emotions by self-regulatory strategies that mitigate the intensity or duration of such emotional states (Saarni, 1999). Emotional utilisation referred to the extent to which adolescents can benefit from emotional changes. A five-point Likert scale was adapted to measure emotional intelligence from different aspects with scores ranging from 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree. Higher average scores indicated higher levels of emotional intelligence. It was found that SSREI has good internal reliability with 0.9 Cronbach's alpha value (Schutte et al., 1998). The Cronbach's alphas of SSREI in this study are 0.89.

Procedures

The survey was disseminated and conducted online using snowball sampling. Once opened the link, participants were shown a participation sheet at the beginning. They were requested to read through the participation sheet containing the title, study objectives, as well as a short summary of eligibility and rights as a participant. Participants were asked whether they were willing to take part in a 20-minute research questionnaire concerning their emotions, family, peers, pets. In order to reduce the misunderstanding that having pets was the premise of participating in the survey, we claimed that they could take part in the current study even though they did not have a pet. Participation was voluntary and all responses were anonymous. Data would be treated confidentially and stored according to GDPR and the university guideline. At the end of the survey, participants could submit their email addresses if they were happy to take part in the raffle with a chance to win a voucher. If participants fully understood and were willing to continue, they were requested to click on a button to the next section with a participant consent form. After reading the consent form, participants should provide their consent by clicking on the button "I agree". The first section of the survey consisted of some demographic questions concerning age, gender, ethnicity and place of residence. The second section was the IPPA, in which participants were asked to rate how often each statement about mother and father typically occurred in their home and rate the feelings about their relationships with close friends. If they did not have a mother/father or person acting like their mother/father (e.g., a stepmother or grandmother), they could skip the corresponding section. The third section was SSREI measuring the self-report trait emotional intelligence. The next sections were followed with a scale for mood and feelings, the GAD-7 measuring the extent of general anxiety symptoms and a scale for aggression. At the end of the survey, there was a debrief form to clarify the purpose of this study. And participants were informed it is impossible to withdraw the submitted answers due to the data confidentiality.

This survey was conducted by the students from the previous grade. This year, the author applied for ethical approval to make statistical analyses based on the existing dataset. Ethical approval for using the data from this study was acquired on 15th May 2021 from the School of Health in Social Science at the University of Edinburgh. After approval, the access to the participant dataset was provided. Neither experimental procedures nor further recruitment was required for the present study. Confidentiality of sensitive data was strictly implemented.

Data screening and analytic strategy

All statistical analysis was conducted using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.0. There was no missing data since participants were not allowed to continue to the next measurement if there were unfinished items in the previous section. In other words, once participants started to respond, they had to respond to every item on that scale. Without missing data, there is no need to make data imputations. All the analyses were based on average scores instead of sum scores since average scores helped to keep the range of scores from different questionnaires to a relatively similar range. After calculating the average score for each variable, data were examined to ensure assumptions for statistical tests. The assumption of normality was examined by skewness and kurtosis values. If the values range from -2 to $+2$, they indicate that the original data is normally distributed. Preliminary analysis showed that all continuous variables were normally distributed since both skewness and kurtosis of these variables ranged from -1 to $+1$ (Table 1), which could also be confirmed by the inspection of the histogram and the P-P plots. The assumption of independent errors was met (Durban-Watson = 1.84). And the assumption of homoscedasticity was met by plots of the standardised residuals against the predicted values. The assumption of linearity was examined and met by the Pearson correlation coefficients between studied variables (Table 3). And there was no evidence showing the presence of multicollinearity since the scores of variance inflation factor (VIF) were less than 10 and the tolerance statistics were less than 0.1.

Given that the existing data met these assumptions for multiple regression, parametric tests were employed on the data analysis. An independent t-test was used to examine the gender differences in the variables. Pearson correlation was employed to assess and compare the strength of associations between these continuous variables of anxiety, emotional intelligence, and maternal attachment. Plus, multiple regression analysis was conducted to examine the mediation and moderation effects. In this study, a bootstrapping approach was adopted to compute the direct, indirect, total and conditional effects because this method allowed the violation of the normality assumption in sampling distribution (Hayes, 2009). A PROCESS macro in SPSS was employed to implement the bootstrapping resampling approach (Preacher et al., 2007). The bootstrapping method repetitively selected samples with replacement and produced bias-corrected 95% confidence intervals for direct effects, indirect effects and total effects, respectively (Preacher & Hayes, 2008). If the 95% confident interval for an effect does not include zero, this effect is considered significant. The bootstrapping method was preferred as it computed the confident intervals for effect sizes instead of p values (Agler & De Boeck, 2017). For moderated mediation analysis, we selected MODEL 14 since it examined the moderating role of gender in the pathway from emotional intelligence to anxiety based on a mediation model.

RESULTS

Descriptive statistics

The mean, standard deviation, range, skewness and kurtosis for the total sample are presented in Table 1. None of the variables was non-normally distributed, suggesting the achievement of the

normality assumption. Therefore, parametric tests could be employed. Table 2 reports the means and standard deviations for the main variables and the gender differences using the independent T-test. There was only a significant gender difference in terms of anxiety symptoms, with a higher level of anxiety among females. And there are no gender differences in terms of emotional intelligence and maternal attachment.

Table 1
 Descriptive statistics for anxiety, emotional intelligence and maternal attachment

Variables	M (SD)	Range	Skewness	Kurtosis
Anxiety	2.37 (0.85)	1.00–4.00	0.30	-0.91
Emotional Intelligence	3.71 (0.51)	2.06–5.00	-0.30	0.39
Maternal Attachment	3.72 (0.81)	1.16–5.00	-0.47	-0.11

Table 2
 Gender differences in anxiety, emotional intelligence and maternal attachment

Variables	Male (n = 43)		Female (n=196)		t	p	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			
Anxiety	2.03	0.79	2.44	0.85	-2.961**	0.003	-0.417
Emotional Intelligence	3.66	0.55	3.72	0.50	-0.646	0.519	-0.056
Maternal Attachment	3.70	0.84	3.73	0.81	-0.224	0.823	-0.031

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Correlation analysis

Table 3 summarises the Pearson's correlation matrix between age, gender, maternal attachment, emotional intelligence and anxiety. Maternal attachment was positively associated with emotional intelligence ($r = 0.40$, $p < 0.01$) while was negatively linked to anxiety ($r = -0.41$, $p < 0.01$). Anxiety was negatively correlated with emotional intelligence ($r = -0.36$, $p < 0.01$) while was positively associated with gender ($r = 0.189$, $p < 0.01$). Despite that gender is a dichotomic variable unsuitable for Pearson's correlation analysis; the coefficient was consistent with the gender difference found in anxiety level in descriptive analysis. There was no evidence showing multicollinearity since no correlation was over 0.7.

Table 3
 Correlations between anxiety, emotional intelligence and maternal attachment

	Age	Gender	Maternal Attachment)	Emotional Intelligence	Anxiety
Age	1				
Gender	0.181**	1			
Maternal attachment	0.084	0.015	1		
Emotional intelligence	0.065	0.042	0.403**	1	

	Age	Gender	Maternal Attachment)	Emotional Intelligence	Anxiety
Anxiety	-0.001	0.189**	-0.414**	-0.363**	1

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, same below

Mediation analysis

The bootstrapping approach with 5000 times of resampling was employed to obtain estimated 95% confident intervals for total, direct and indirect effect. Table 4 shows the unstandardised coefficients and significances for the direct, indirect and total effects. The total effect of maternal attachment on anxiety was significant ($B = -0.433$, 95% CI $[-0.555, -0.311]$, $p < 0.001$; c path). After including EI as the mediating variable, there was a significant effect of maternal attachment on EI ($B = 0.253$, 95% CI $[0.180, 0.327]$, $p < 0.001$; a path) and of EI on anxiety ($B = -0.391$, 95% CI $[-0.598, -0.185]$, $p < 0.001$; b path). Also, the direct impact of maternal attachment on anxiety remained significant ($B = -0.334$, 95% CI $[-0.467, -0.201]$, $p < 0.001$; c' path). Given that the bootstrapped 95% confident interval (95% CI) did not include zero, the indirect effect was significant ($B = -0.100$, 95% CI $[-0.166, -0.038]$, $p < 0.001$; a*b path), suggesting a partial mediating role of emotional intelligence (EI) between maternal attachment and anxiety. Figure 2 shows the different path coefficients in the mediating model.

Table 4

Unstandardised coefficients for total, direct and indirect effect

	B (Unstandardised coefficients)	SE	p	95% CI
Total Effect	-0.433	0.618	<0.001	$[-0.555, -0.311]$
Direct Effect	-0.334	0.068	<0.001	$[-0.467, -0.201]$
Indirect Effect	-0.100	0.033	<0.001	$[-0.166, -0.038]$

Figure 2

The mediating role of emotional intelligence between maternal attachment and anxiety

Moderated mediation analysis

According to Aiken and West (1991), regression analyses of the interaction term was recommended to examine the moderating effect. If the interaction term could significantly predict the dependent variable, there was a moderating effect. The level of anxiety was coded as the outcome variable (Y) and maternal attachment was coded as the independent variable (X). Emotional intelligence acted as the mediator variable (M) and gender as the moderator for the relationship between emotional intelligence and anxiety (W). For Hypothesis 4, a moderated mediation analysis was performed by PROCESS macro, which automatically generated the interaction term of emotional intelligence*gender (M*W). According to Hayes (2009), MODEL 14 (A moderated mediation model) was selected to examine the potential moderating effect of gender in the association between emotional intelligence and anxiety. Table 5 presents unstandardised regression coefficients of X, M, W and M*W on predicting the level of anxiety. The interaction term (M*W) between gender and emotional intelligence significantly predicted anxiety, indicating the effect of emotional intelligence on anxiety was dependent on gender. Specifically, emotional intelligence significantly predicted anxiety in females ($B = -0.530$, $p < 0.001$, 95% CI = [-0.812, -0.248]), but not in males ($B=0.085$, $p = 0.722$, 95% CI = [-0.384, 0.553]). Table 6 shows unstandardised regression coefficients for conditional indirect effects. Emotional intelligence only mediated the indirect effect of maternal attachment on anxiety in females (Indirect effect = -0.134, 95% CI= [-0.209, -0.065]), but not in males (Indirect effect = 0.021, 95% CI = [-0.100, 0.137]), which meant the mediating effect was conditional by gender. Furthermore, the overall model was significant (Index = -0.156, $SE = 0.066$, 95% CI = [-0.292, -0.031]), indicating that there was a moderated mediation model. The moderated mediation model explained 28.1% of the variance in anxiety ($R^2 = 0.281$, $F(234, 4) = 16.822$, $p < 0.001$). Figure 3 shows the moderated mediation model.

Table 5
Unstandardised coefficients for predicting anxiety in the moderated mediation model

	B (Unstandardised)	SE	p	95% CI
Maternal Attachment(X)	-0.334	0.065	<0.001	[-0.462, -0.205]
Emotional Intelligence(M)	0.699	0.484	0.150	[-0.254, 1.652]
Gender(W)	2.706	0.959	0.005	[0.816, 4.596]
Emotional Intelligence*Gender(M*W)	-0.614	0.266	0.022	[-1.138, -0.091]

Table 6
Conditional indirect effects in males and females

	B (Unstandardized indirect effect)	SE	p	95% CI
Male(n=43)	0.021	0.238	0.722	[-0.384, 0.553]
Female(n=196)	-0.530	0.143	<0.001	[-0.812, -0.248]

Figure 3. The moderated mediation model

DISCUSSION

The purpose of the current study was to investigate how adolescent-mother attachment influences anxiety among adolescents and young people, with consideration of adolescent gender. Consistent with hypotheses, the results showed there was a significant indirect effect from attachment to anxiety through emotional intelligence in female adolescents and young adults, but not in males. These findings highlighted the crucial role of emotional intelligence in the development of anxiety during adolescence and stress the idea that gender should be taken into consideration in explaining the pathway from emotional intelligence to anxiety. Our results supported the first hypothesis that maternal attachment could negatively predict anxiety among adolescents and young adults. Correlation analysis revealed that the level of anxiety was negatively associated with maternal attachment. Regression analysis showed that anxiety could be predicted from maternal attachment. Such findings were consistent with previous studies demonstrating a strong negative correlation between maternal attachment and anxiety (Bender et al., 2012; Colonnesi et al., 2011; Read et al., 2018).

In terms of the second hypothesis, maternal attachment had a significant impact on emotional intelligence among adolescents and young people as hypothesized. More specifically, secure maternal attachment demonstrated a positive effect on emotional intelligence in youth, which was in line with previous work (Bender et al., 2012; Brumariu et al., 2012; Cherry et al., 2013). Emotional intelligence was composed of a set of capabilities of understanding, expressing and regulating emotions, which might gradually develop from early attachment experiences. It was revealed from the result that individuals with higher attachment security exhibited higher levels of emotional intelligence, meaning more securely attached individuals were more capable of understanding and regulating emotions. Consistent with this finding, Krikorian (2002) suggested that attachment insecurity was negatively associated with the motivation to manage emotions while high attachment avoidance was related to the low capacity of emotional management. With a low motivation to manage emotions, insecurely attached adolescents might have fewer opportunities to engage in the socialisation process and obtain fewer social experiences on understanding and regulating the emotions of others and the self, which was presented with low emotional intelligence. This idea was further supported by the work of Lopes et al. (2003). They found that emotional management ability was strongly associated with social behaviour and the daily interactions with families, friends and peers, which contributed to the abilities of emotional management since humans are social creatures.

According to Bowlby (1982), early caregiving experiences were internalized in internal working models that provided unwritten patterns for how individuals experienced and coped with distressing emotions. Avoidantly attached individuals characterized by emotional suppression were less capable of perceiving and understanding emotional information (Cherry et al., 2013) because they normally tended to detach themselves from distressing emotions. As a consequence, they might not obtain sufficient experiences to understand emotions. In contrast, anxiously attached ones were prone to employing hyperactivating emotional strategies such as acting out or losing their temper, which may deteriorate the ability of emotion regulation. Therefore, it can be inferred that insecure attachment may influence the different aspects of emotional intelligence, including emotional understanding and regulation. Future studies can explore the sub-dimensions of EI to examine which components are among the most affected by attachment insecurity in youth.

Addressing the third hypothesis, emotional intelligence mediated the association between attachment and anxiety. This was to say that not only emotional intelligence was predicted from attachment, but also it negatively predicted anxiety. This finding was consistent with previous work proving the effect of emotional intelligence on anxiety (Hassan & Achugbu, 2010; Mashhadi, 2010; Morón & Biolik-Morón, 2021; Resurrección et al., 2014). In addition, previous studies found that emotional clarity and emotional repair capacity acted as a predictor of anxiety symptoms (Mashhadi,

2010), which suggested that a higher level of emotional repair and clarity could predict a lower level of anxiety. And emotional attention could positively predict anxiety (Salguero & Palomera et al., 2012). In summary, adolescents with higher emotional intelligence may be more capable of recognizing and alleviating anxiety due to higher emotional clarity and repair capability with less emotional attention. Therefore, they are less likely to be disturbed by anxiety in the long term. Besides, it was found that the self-awareness component of emotional intelligence significantly predicted anxiety (Saeed & Dortaj, 2018). It was suggested that adolescents with higher emotional intelligence were more capable of understanding one's internal states, preferences, intuitions and thus might develop a clearer self-awareness contributing to the establishment of self-identity. A clearer self-identity might help to alleviate anxiety since the main task during late adolescence was to establish a sense of self-identity about who I am (Erikson, 1950). Once failed, adolescents and young people were likely to feel a sense of uncertainty and thus were more anxious. Emotional intelligence might help youth find a clear image of the self and thus relieve anxiety towards self-identity in this developmental stage.

Moreover, anxiety levels are partially influenced by individuals' coping strategies, which are affected by emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence has been found to significantly predict various components of coping strategies, including cognitive appraisal and the seeking of social support (Moradi et al., 2011). It is suggested that individuals with higher emotional intelligence possess greater cognitive flexibility, enabling them to evaluate and reappraise thoughts more effectively, which contributes to reducing anxiety (Dryman & Heimberg, 2018; Hofmann et al., 2009)

Additionally, adolescents with higher emotional intelligence are more likely to access social support, which can help alleviate anxiety. This is because emotional intelligence is associated with higher-quality interpersonal relationships (Gignac et al., 2005), fewer negative peer interactions, and enhanced social skills (Saeed & Dortaj, 2018). As a result, emotionally intelligent individuals are more likely to receive support from others and, consequently, experience lower levels of anxiety

Individuals with higher emotional intelligence tend to exhibit lower emotional attention, greater emotional clarity and repair, heightened self-awareness, more adaptive coping strategies, and stronger social support networks, all of which contribute to reduced vulnerability to anxiety compared to those with lower emotional intelligence.

As for the fourth hypothesis, the indirect effect of maternal attachment on anxiety was dependent on gender, such that it was significant only in females, but not in males. This suggested that adolescent gender should be taken into account in explaining the developmental pathway from maternal attachment to anxiety during late adolescence and young adulthood. More specifically, the relationship between emotional intelligence and anxiety was contingent upon gender. Emotional intelligence only predicted anxiety for females, but not for males. The moderating effect of gender was a bit out of expectation since there was no gender difference found in terms of emotional intelligence and maternal attachment security in the section of descriptive statistics, though females had a higher level of anxiety than males. The significant indirect effect for females may be attributed to gender expectations. In general, females were taught to be fearful and dependent, while males were taught to be courageous and independent (Yang & McNair, 2021). Thus, females would be likely to feel more stressed than males when being faced with similar situations due to personal traits developed from gender expectations.

Plus, the failure of understanding emotions was likely to induce higher levels of anxiety in females than in males since females were more relation-oriented than males (Gutermuth & Hamstra, 2024). They had higher levels of expectation towards interpersonal relationships than males (Rose & Rudolph, 2006; Weymouth et al., 2016). Once they could not understand and regulate emotions

which were revealed by emotional intelligence ability, females would be more easily distressed and vulnerable to the failure of understanding and regulating emotions. Therefore, lower levels of emotional intelligence had a greater impact on anxiety in females. The lower quality of maternal attachment in females was also likely to have a more detrimental effect and thus increased higher levels of anxiety than males since females appeared to be more adversely affected by poorer adolescent-parent attachment (Perry et al., 2017). Thus, the indirect effect of maternal attachment on anxiety was only significant in females. However, there was no similar finding supporting the moderating effect of gender in the association between emotional intelligence and anxiety since this study was the first one, to the author's knowledge, to explore the moderating role of gender in the association between maternal attachment, emotional intelligence and anxiety. Moreover, this finding was inconsistent with previous studies demonstrating that emotional intelligence predicted mental health outcomes such as depression only in males (Lishner et al., 2011; Salguero & Extremera et al., 2012). Plus, the non-significant effect of emotional intelligence on anxiety in males might be underpowered due to the limited sample size ($N = 43$). Despite that a bootstrapping resampling procedure was employed to estimate the confident interval of the regression coefficient, the unbalanced sample proportion might affect the reliability of results. Therefore, the moderating effect of gender should be carefully re-examined with more sufficient samples in males to detect whether the effect of emotional intelligence on anxiety was still conditional by gender. The moderating effect of gender in the present study should be carefully generalized.

Strengths and limitations

The current study included several limitations that should be acknowledged and addressed in future research. First, as this study employed a cross-sectional design, the direction of causality between the variables could not be confirmed. Future studies could adopt a longitudinal design, measuring attachment, emotional intelligence, and anxiety at multiple time points during adolescence to examine the presence of cross-lagged correlations. Such studies would help establish temporal precedence and clarify whether causal relationships exist between attachment, emotional intelligence, and anxiety.

Second, the moderating effect of gender may have been limited due to the relatively small number of male participants. Although the male sample exceeded 30, the regression coefficient for the effect of emotional intelligence on anxiety among males may still have been underpowered, falling below the commonly accepted threshold of 80%. Future studies should aim to recruit a larger and more balanced sample by gender to better assess the moderating role of gender in the relationship between emotional intelligence and anxiety.

Additionally, due to the limited available literature on the impact of paternal attachment on emotional intelligence, this variable was not included in the present analysis. Future research could explore this area further by examining the influence of paternal attachment on emotional intelligence and anxiety, as well as the potential moderating effect of gender.

Finally, the mediation analysis of emotional intelligence in this study was based on overall average scores and did not examine specific sub-dimensions of emotional intelligence to determine which components most significantly contribute to the relationship between attachment and anxiety in adolescence and young adulthood. However, the structure of the SSREI remains contested, with past studies reporting inconsistent dimensional compositions (Ciarrochi et al., 2001; Gignac et al., 2005; Schutte et al., 1998), rendering the interpretation of subscales unclear. Future researchers should conduct reliability testing or confirmatory factor analysis before engaging in subscale analysis, to ensure the reliability and validity of the emotional intelligence sub-dimensions. This would enable a

deeper and more precise understanding of which specific components of emotional intelligence most strongly influence anxiety.

Implications for future research

As discussed above, the present study offers several implications for future research. First, longitudinal studies are necessary to determine not only the direction but also the potential causal relationships among the variables. For instance, van Eijck et al. (2012) identified a negative bidirectional association between paternal attachment and generalised anxiety disorder (GAD), indicating that attachment and anxiety may influence each other in a dynamic interplay during adolescence. It is plausible that anxiety can partly stem from attachment insecurity developed in early experiences, while persistent anxiety may, in turn, erode the quality of adolescent–parent attachment. This does not imply a simple cause–effect relationship but rather suggests a reciprocal influence that evolves over time. Future research should therefore examine the longitudinal associations between these constructs.

Moreover, the moderating role of gender in the mediation model reinforces the need to incorporate gender as a variable when examining the development of anxiety in late adolescence and early adulthood. The current literature remains limited in its exploration of gender-specific effects within attachment frameworks. Considering gender in future studies may enhance our understanding of the distinct developmental pathways from attachment to anxiety and support the design of gender-sensitive interventions. Gender-informed insights could help practitioners tailor interventions to align with the specific mechanisms underlying anxiety in different genders.

Given that the moderated mediation model accounted for 28.1% of the variance in anxiety, it is evident that other contributing factors remain unaccounted for. Future research should seek to identify additional variables involved in the aetiology and maintenance of anxiety, aiming to construct a more comprehensive model that captures multiple developmental trajectories from maternal attachment to anxiety. Such models would allow for comparative analyses of the effect sizes of various factors, thereby enabling practitioners to focus on those with greater predictive power when designing targeted interventions.

CONCLUSION

The present study was the first to examine the mechanisms from maternal attachment to anxiety via emotional intelligence, with consideration of gender. It was found that trait emotional intelligence was a significant predictor of anxiety in older adolescents and young adults. Additionally, emotional intelligence mediated the relationship between maternal attachment and anxiety in female adolescents and young people, but not in males. Specifically, the effect of emotional intelligence on anxiety was conditional by gender, with a significant effect only in females but not in males. However, the moderating effect of gender should be carefully generalised due to potential problems.

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REFERENCES

- Acharya, S., & Relojo, D. (2017). Examining the role of cognitive distortion and parental bonding in depressive symptoms among male adolescents: A randomised crossover trial. *Journal of Innovation in Psychology, Education and Didactics*, 21(1), 7–20. <https://doi.org/d9m6>
- Agler, R., & De Boeck, P. (2017). On the interpretation and use of mediation: Multiple perspectives on mediation analysis. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8, 1984. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.01984>
- Aiken, L. S., & West, S. G. (1991). *Multiple regression: Testing and interpreting interactions*. Sage Publications.
- Armsden, G. C., & Greenberg, M. T. (1987). The inventory of parent and peer attachment: Individual differences and their relationship to psychological well-being in adolescence. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 16(5), 427–454. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02202939>
- Bender, P. K., Esbjørn, B. H., Sømhøvd, M., & Pons, F. (2012). Anxiety in children and adolescents: The roles of attachment and emotion dysregulation. *Neuropsychiatrie de l'Enfance et de l'Adolescence*, 60(5, Supplement), S161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuoenf.2012.04.211>
- Bonab, B. G., & Koohsar, A. A. H. (2011). Relation between quality of attachment and anxiety in delinquent adolescents. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 30, 959–962. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.10.186>
- Borawski, D., Sojda, M., Rychlewska, K., & Wajs, T. (2022). Attached but lonely: Emotional intelligence as a mediator and moderator between attachment styles and loneliness. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(22), 14831. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192214831>
- Bourne, S. V., Korom, M., & Dozier, M. (2022). Consequences of inadequate caregiving for children's attachment, neurobiological development, and adaptive functioning. *Clinical Child and Family Psychology Review*, 25(1), 166–181. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10567-021-00368-1>
- Bowlby, J. (1982). Attachment and loss: Retrospect and prospect. *American Journal of Orthopsychiatry*, 52(4), 664–678. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1939-0025.1982.tb01456.x>
- Brumariu, L. E., & Kerns, K. A. (2008). Mother–child attachment and social anxiety symptoms in middle childhood. *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology*, 29(5), 393–402. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appdev.2008.06.002>
- Brumariu, L. E., Kerns, K. A., & Seibert, A. (2012). Mother–child attachment, emotion regulation, and anxiety symptoms in middle childhood. *Personal Relationships*, 19(3), 569–585. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-6811.2011.01379.x>
- Cejudo, J., Rodrigo-Ruiz, D., López-Delgado, M. L., & Losada, L. (2018). Emotional intelligence and its relationship with levels of social anxiety and stress in adolescents. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(6), 1073. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15061073>
- Chang, E. C. (2018). Relationship between loneliness and symptoms of anxiety and depression in African American men and women: Evidence for gender as a moderator. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 120, 138–143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2017.08.035>
- Cherry, M. G., Fletcher, I., & O'Sullivan, H. (2013). Exploring the relationships among attachment, emotional intelligence and communication. *Medical Education*, 47(3), 317–325. <https://doi.org/10.1111/medu.12115>
- Ciarrochi, J., Chan, A. Y. C., & Bajgar, J. (2001). Measuring emotional intelligence in adolescents. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 31(7), 1105–1119. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-8869\(00\)00207-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-8869(00)00207-5)
- Collins, N. L., Cooper, M. L., Albino, A., & Allard, L. (2002). Psychosocial vulnerability from adolescence to adulthood: A prospective study of attachment style differences in relationship functioning and partner choice. *Journal of Personality*, 70(6), 965–1008. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-6494.05029>

- Colonnesi, C., Draijer, E. M., Stams, G. J. J. M., Van der Bruggen, C. O., Bögels, S. M., & Noom, M. J. (2011). The relation between insecure attachment and child anxiety: A meta-analytic review. *Journal of Clinical Child & Adolescent Psychology, 40*(4), 630–645. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15374416.2011.581623>
- Dryman, M. T., & Heimberg, R. G. (2018). Emotion regulation in social anxiety and depression: A systematic review of expressive suppression and cognitive reappraisal. *Clinical Psychology Review, 65*, 17–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpr.2018.07.004>
- Dykas, M. J., & Cassidy, J. (2011). Attachment and the processing of social information across the life span: Theory and evidence. *Psychological Bulletin, 137*(1), 19–46. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0021367>
- Erikson, E. H. (1950). *Childhood and society*. W. W. Norton & Company. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2572742>
- Faul, F., Erdfelder, E., Lang, A.-G., & Buchner, A. (2007). G*Power 3: A flexible statistical power analysis program for the social, behavioral, and biomedical sciences. *Behavior Research Methods, 39*(2), 175–191. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03193146>
- Fernández-Merino, B. C. J. M. (2020). Anxiety and emotional intelligence: Comparisons between combat sports, gender and levels using the Trait Meta-Mood Scale and the Inventory of Situations and Anxiety Response. *Frontiers in Psychology, 11*, 130. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00130>
- García-Sancho, E., Salguero, J. M., & Fernández-Berrocal, P. (2014). Relationship between emotional intelligence and aggression: A systematic review. *Aggression and Violent Behavior, 19*(5), 584–591. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.avb.2014.07.007>
- Ghandour, M., Salloum, D. A., Jaber, M. H., Abou Orm, G., Ghosn, A., Jaber, S., Abd El Nour, H., Chalfoun, A., Dagher, T., & Hanna, B. (2025). A comparative meta-analysis of the efficacy and safety of arthroscopic versus open surgery in patients with lateral epicondylitis. *Journal of Orthopaedics, 59*, 41–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jor.2024.07.018>
- Gignac, G. E., Palmer, B. R., Manocha, R., & Stough, C. (2005). An examination of the factor structure of the Schutte Self-Report Emotional Intelligence (SSREI) scale via confirmatory factor analysis. *Personality and Individual Differences, 39*(6), 1029–1042. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2005.03.014>
- Gomez-Baya, D., Mendoza, R., Paino, S., & de Matos, M. G. (2017). Perceived emotional intelligence as a predictor of depressive symptoms during mid-adolescence: A two-year longitudinal study on gender differences. *Personality and Individual Differences, 104*, 303–312. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2016.08.022>
- Goodwin, R. D., & Styron, T. H. (2012). Perceived quality of early paternal relationships and mental health in adulthood. *The Journal of Nervous and Mental Disease, 200*(9), 791–795. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NMD.0b013e318266f87c>
- Guo, X., Meng, Z., Huang, G., Fan, J., Zhou, W., Ling, W., Jiang, J., Long, J., & Su, L. (2016). Meta-analysis of the prevalence of anxiety disorders in mainland China from 2000 to 2015. *Scientific Reports, 6*, 28033. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep28033>
- Gutermuth, D., & Hamstra, M. R. W. (2024). Promotion focus is valued in men more than in women. *Journal of Organizational Behavior, 45*(5), 764–781. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.2781>
- Hassan, S. A., & Achugbu, C. (2010). Exploring the relationship of emotional intelligence with mental health among early adolescence. *International Journal of Psychological Studies, 2*(2), 205–219. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijps.v2n2p209>
- Hayes, A. F. (2009). Beyond Baron and Kenny: Statistical mediation analysis in the new millennium. *Communication Monographs, 76*(4), 408–420. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03637750903310360>
- He, X. Y., Li, C. B., Qian, J., Cui, H. S., & Wu, W. Y. (2010). Reliability and validity of a generalized anxiety disorder scale in general hospital outpatients. *Shanghai Archives of Psychiatry, 22*(4), 200–203.

- Hofmann, S. G., Heering, S., Sawyer, A. T., & Asnaani, A. (2009). How to handle anxiety: The effects of reappraisal, acceptance, and suppression strategies on anxious arousal. *Behaviour Research and Therapy*, 47(5), 389–394. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brat.2009.02.010>
- Kafetsios, K. (2004). Attachment and emotional intelligence abilities across the life course. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 37(1), 129–145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2003.08.006>
- Karakuş, M. (2013). Emotional intelligence and negative feelings: A gender specific moderated mediation model. *Educational Studies*, 39(1), 68–82. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03055698.2012.671514>
- Krikorian, M. (2002). *Emotional intelligence in relation to attachment type* (Doctoral dissertation). University of Detroit Mercy.
- Lanciano, T., Curci, A., Kafetsios, K., Elia, L., & Zammuner, V. L. (2012). Attachment and dysfunctional rumination: The mediating role of emotional intelligence abilities. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 53(6), 753–758. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2012.05.027>
- Lee, J. Y. S., Whittingham, K., & Mitchell, A. E. (2022). Childhood experiences of being parented, adult attachment, psychological inflexibility, social engagement, and mental health of autistic adults. *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 130, 104343. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2022.104343>
- Li, N., Zhang, W., Li, D., Mai, Y., & Xing, W. (2009). Parent-adolescent attachment, emotional intelligence, and aggression in adolescence. *Psychological Development and Education*, 25(2), 91–96. <https://doi.org/10.1037/e622522009-001>
- Lim, S. A., You, S., & Ha, D. (2015). Parental emotional support and adolescent happiness: Mediating roles of self-esteem and emotional intelligence. *Applied Research in Quality of Life*, 10(4), 631–646. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11482-014-9344-0>
- Lishner, D. A., Swim, E. R., Hong, P. Y., & Vitacco, M. J. (2011). Psychopathy and ability emotional intelligence: Widespread or limited association among facets? *Personality and Individual Differences*, 50(7), 1029–1033. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2011.01.018>
- Lopes, P. N., Brackett, M. A., Nezlek, J. B., Schütz, A., Sellin, I., & Salovey, P. (2004). Emotional intelligence and social interaction. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 30(8), 1018–1034. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0146167204264762>
- Lopes, P. N., Salovey, P., & Straus, R. (2003). Emotional intelligence, personality, and the perceived quality of social relationships. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 35(3), 641–658. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-8869\(02\)00242-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-8869(02)00242-8)
- Marks, A. D. G., Horrocks, K. A., & Schutte, N. S. (2016). Emotional intelligence mediates the relationship between insecure attachment and subjective health outcomes. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 98, 188–192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2016.03.038>
- Martins, A., Ramalho, N., & Morin, E. (2010). A comprehensive meta-analysis of the relationship between emotional intelligence and health. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 49(6), 554–564. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2010.05.029>
- Mashhadi, A. (2010). On the relationship between emotional intelligence and its components with symptoms of anxiety. *Journal of Fundamentals of Mental Health*, 12(48), 61–252.
- Mazzone, A., Yanagida, T., Camodeca, M., & Strohmeier, D. (2021). Information processing of social exclusion: Links with bullying, moral disengagement and guilt. *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology*, 75, 101292. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appdev.2021.101292>
- Mikulincer, M., Shaver, P. R., & Pereg, D. (2003). Attachment theory and affect regulation: The dynamics, development, and cognitive consequences of attachment-related strategies. *Motivation and Emotion*, 27(2), 77–102. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1024515519160>
- Mohammadi, M. R., Pourdehghan, P., Mostafavi, S., Hooshyari, Z., Ahmadi, N., & Khaleghi, A. (2020). Generalized anxiety disorder: Prevalence, predictors, and comorbidity in children and adolescents. *Journal of Anxiety Disorders*, 73, 102234. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.janxdis.2020.102234>

- Moradi, A., Pishva, N., Ehsan, H. B., Hadadi, P., & Pouladi, F. (2011). The relationship between coping strategies and emotional intelligence. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 30, 748–751. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.10.145>
- Moroń, M., & Biolik-Moroń, M. (2021). Trait emotional intelligence and emotional experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic outbreak in Poland: A daily diary study. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 168, 110348. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2020.110348>
- Navas-Casado, M. L., García-Sancho, E., & Salguero, J. M. (2023). Associations between maladaptive and adaptive emotion regulation strategies and aggressive behavior: A systematic review. *Aggression and Violent Behavior*, 71, 101845. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.avb.2023.101845>
- Nielsen, S. K. K., Lønfeldt, N., Wolitzky-Taylor, K. B., Hageman, I., Vangkilde, S., & Daniel, S. I. F. (2017). Adult attachment style and anxiety – The mediating role of emotion regulation. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 218, 253–259. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2017.04.047>
- Pace, U., Zappulla, C., & Di Maggio, R. (2016). The mediating role of perceived peer support in the relation between quality of attachment and internalizing problems in adolescence: A longitudinal perspective. *Attachment & Human Development*, 18(5), 508–524. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616734.2016.1198919>
- Pan, Y., Zhang, D., Liu, Y., Ran, G., & Wang, Z. (2016). Attachment and internalizing symptoms: The mediating role of regulatory emotional self-efficacy among Chinese young adolescents. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 101, 360–365. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2016.06.030>
- Perry, R. E., Blair, C., & Sullivan, R. M. (2017). Neurobiology of infant attachment: Attachment despite adversity and parental programming of emotionality. *Current Opinion in Psychology*, 17, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsy.2017.04.022>
- Petrides, K. V., & Mavroveli, S. (2018). Theory and applications of trait emotional intelligence. *Psychology: The Journal of the Hellenic Psychological Society*, 23(1), 24–36. https://doi.org/10.12681/psy_hps.23016
- Pilao, S. J., Relojo, D., Tubon, G., & Subida, M. (2016). Examination of factors affecting the feeling of loneliness among the elderly: Implications for intervention. *Journal on Innovation in Psychology, Education and Didactics*, 20(1), 15–26. <https://doi.org/gbzz>
- Preacher, K. J., & Hayes, A. F. (2008). Asymptotic and resampling strategies for assessing and comparing indirect effects in multiple mediator models. *Behavior Research Methods*, 40(3), 879–891. <https://doi.org/10.3758/brm.40>
- Preacher, K. J., Rucker, D. D., & Hayes, A. F. (2007). Addressing moderated mediation hypotheses: Theory, methods, and prescriptions. *Multivariate Behavioral Research*, 42(1), 185–227. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00273170701341316>
- Read, D. L., Clark, G. I., Rock, A. J., & Coventry, W. L. (2018). Adult attachment and social anxiety: The mediating role of emotion regulation strategies. *PLOS ONE*, 13(12), e0207514. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0207514>
- Resurrección, D. M., Salguero, J. M., & Ruiz-Aranda, D. (2014). Emotional intelligence and psychological maladjustment in adolescence: A systematic review. *Journal of Adolescence*, 37(4), 461–472. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adolescence.2014.03.012>
- Rose, A. J., & Rudolph, K. D. (2006). A review of sex differences in peer relationship processes: Potential trade-offs for the emotional and behavioral development of girls and boys. *Psychological Bulletin*, 132(1), 98–131. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.132.1.98> SCIRP
- Rutter, L. A., & Brown, T. A. (2017). Psychometric properties of the Generalized Anxiety Disorder Scale-7 (GAD-7) in outpatients with anxiety and mood disorders. *Journal of Psychopathology and Behavioral Assessment*, 39(1), 140–146. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10862-016-9571-9>
- Saarni, C. (1999). *The development of emotional competence*. Guilford Press. SCIRP
- Saeed, N., & Dortaj, F. (2018). The relationship between academic self-efficacy and emotional intelligence with anxiety in the students of distance education. *Journal of Research in Educational Systems*, 12(41), 111–131.

- Salguero, J. M., Extremera, N., & Fernández-Berrocal, P. (2012). Emotional intelligence and depression: The moderator role of gender. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 53(1), 29–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2012.02.006>
- Salguero, J. M., Palomera, R., & Fernández-Berrocal, P. (2012). Perceived emotional intelligence as predictor of psychological adjustment in adolescents: A 1-year prospective study. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 27(1), 21–34. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10212-011-0063-8>
- Salovey, P., & Mayer, J. D. (1990). Emotional intelligence. *Imagination, Cognition and Personality*, 9(3), 185–211. <https://doi.org/10.2190/DUGG-P24E-52WK-6CDGSCIRP>
- Scarlat, E. M. (2021). The role of cognitive schemas in the relationship between attachment style and emotional intelligence. *Studia Doctoralia*, 12(1), 54–69. <https://doi.org/10.47040/sd/sdpsych.v12i1.123>
- Schutte, N. S., Malouff, J. M., Hall, L. E., Haggerty, D. J., Cooper, J. T., Golden, C. J., & Dornheim, L. (1998). Development and validation of a measure of emotional intelligence. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 25(2), 167–177. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-8869\(98\)00001-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-8869(98)00001-4)
- Silberg, J., Rutter, M., Neale, M., & Eaves, L. (2001). Genetic moderation of environmental risk for depression and anxiety in adolescent girls. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 179(2), 116–121. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.179.2.116>
- Śmieja, M., Orzechowski, J., & Stolarski, M. S. (2014). TIE: An ability test of emotional intelligence. *PLOS ONE*, 9(7), e103484. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0103484>
- Spitzer, R. L., Kroenke, K., Williams, J. B. W., & Löwe, B. (2006). A brief measure for assessing generalized anxiety disorder: The GAD-7. *Archives of Internal Medicine*, 166(10), 1092–1097. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archinte.166.10.1092>
- Unni, D. (2015). The effect of emotional intelligence on parent & peer attachment among adolescents (Master's thesis).
- van Eijck, F. E., Branje, S. J. T., Hale, W. W., & Meeus, W. H. J. (2012). Longitudinal associations between perceived parent-adolescent attachment relationship quality and generalized anxiety disorder symptoms in adolescence. *Journal of Abnormal Child Psychology*, 40(6), 871–883. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10802-012-9613-z>
- Walker, S. A., Double, K. S., Kunst, H., Zhang, M., & MacCann, C. (2022). Emotional intelligence and attachment in adulthood: A meta-analysis. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 184, 111174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2021.111174>
- Warren, S. L., Huston, L., Egeland, B., & Sroufe, L. A. (1997). Child and adolescent anxiety disorders and early attachment. *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*, 36(5), 637–644. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00004583-199705000-00014>
- Weymouth, B. B., Buehler, C., Zhou, N., & Henson, R. A. (2016). A meta-analysis of parent–adolescent conflict: Disagreement, hostility, and youth maladjustment. *Journal of Family Theory & Review*, 8(1), 95–112. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jftr.12126>
- Wojciechowski, J., Stolarski, M., & Matthews, G. (2014). Emotional intelligence and mismatching expressive and verbal messages: A contribution to detection of deception. *PLOS ONE*, 9(3), e92570. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0092570>
- Wołyńczyk-Gmaj, D., Jakubczyk, A., Trucco, E. M., Kobyliński, P., Zaorska, J., Gmaj, B., & Kopera, M. (2022). Emotional dysregulation, anxiety symptoms and insomnia in individuals with alcohol use disorder. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(5), 2700. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19052700>
- Woodward, L. J., & Fergusson, D. M. (2001). Life course outcomes of young people with anxiety disorders in adolescence. *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*, 40(9), 1086–1093. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00004583-200109000-00018>
- Yang, Y., & McNair, D. E. (2021). Chinese male early childhood education teachers' perceptions of their roles and professional development. *Gender and Education*, 33(4), 468–482. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09540253.2020.1786010>

Zhou, S., Zhang, L., Wang, L., Guo, Z., Wang, J., Chen, J., Liu, M., Chen, X., & Chen, J. (2020). Prevalence and socio-demographic correlates of psychological health problems in Chinese adolescents during the outbreak of COVID-19. *European Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*, 29(6), 749–758. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00787-020-01541-4>